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**TEMPLATE FORM ON FACULTY FULL-BLOWN PROPOSAL AND OR
FINAL IMRAD (Publishable) MANUSCRIPT**

**TITLE : Bolstering Hybrid Facilitation of Learner -Centered Teaching Amidst the
Challenges of the Post – Pandemic Era**

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April 2023

ABSTRACT

The study surfaced the emerging level of readiness, challenges and transition pathway from temporary on-line modality of delivery to face -to-face learning with full swing hybrid facilitation of learner -centered teaching experiences in the post-pandemic era. Out from the 442 tertiary respondents, the level of readiness was rated to a great extent with a mean score of 3.6. The adjustments made in diverse ways were the dominant challenges that confronted the teaching - learning process. Hybrid modality of learning significantly served as the saving portal to incessantly respond to the emerging needs of time. Challenging dimensions are forwarded as basis of intervention to keep pace with the evolving demands and to address concerns and issues in the continuity of education. Facilitation of learner-centered teaching opened-up diverse avenues and means to bolster, improve and sustain practices and pedagogies among teachers and students in the post-pandemic era. With the sudden shift on on-line learning to face-to-face modality, challenges and barriers encountered were re-evaluated to re-appropriate strategies and methods as pathway for more efficacy on hybrid learning. Management and scaffolding measures through inspired pedagogies remain paramount in the educational field.

Keywords: hybrid learning, facilitation, pedagogy, learner- centered teaching, transition, readiness

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INTRODUCTION

Education is ever evolving hence the need to bolster practices through scaffold and management of the facilitation of hybrid learner-centered teaching. Effective pedagogy should be maximized to respond to the emerging needs of learners in a full swing face-to-face modality. The existing curriculum becomes functional only if it fulfills its task as the heart and soul of the educational processes. How mentors approach their teaching style and blend theories in classroom instruction becomes paramount in the teaching-learning repertoire. They give feedback and the assessment they set. Creation of hybrid learning environment becomes a paramount entry point in the teaching-learning process. Distance learning has evolved over the years in the multiplicity of circumstances. It is readily known as Open and Distance Learning (ODL). Generally, it is a form of open learning where students can pursue a preferred course or subject without any classroom presence. According to UNESCO (2004), ODL has developed into a significant worldwide system in resolving issues of access to education. In another hindsight, distance learning is thought of to be a new term since the conventional way of accessing education is through face-to-face instruction. Synonymously, it is referred to hybrid learning. The term has been popularly used and utilized for about 100 years, which started through correspondence courses, one of the early forms conducted in Europe (Valentine, 2002).

Further, as described in another fashion, such can be attributed to correspondence courses and programs that are provided by a school institution wherein instructional materials are provided through electronic transmission or mail to learners. In the Philippines, distance learning started to be commercialized in the earlier years of 2000 together with the improvement of the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) sector both in educational institutions and government facilities although there were challenges encountered due to the absence of substantial ICT facilities to sustain the service (Dela Cruz, Garcia, & Galeon, 2019). Most of the Higher Education Institution has gone back gradually with the face-to-face modality and has transitioned efficaciously to respond to the various challenges of post-pandemic era wherein hybrid learning remains to be the choice not to be evaded. Hybrid learning is cognizant of the inclusion of formidable paradigm of shifting interventions in providing the four pillars of education. With unprecedented events, there is a continuing goal to bolster every learning possibility in facilitating learner-centered teaching.

The pandemic era for the past two years brought several disruptions in the whole web of human life around the globe. Academically speaking, this however are resolved with the adaptation of hybrid facilitation of learner-centered teaching. Much less, even the current situation still poses several challenges. Hence, continuing innovations should be put into place by bolstering hybrid learning. More than ever, there is an inevitable need to provide learners the expected learning aligned to the competencies of their chosen program and area of discipline. The ever-evolving needs of students has given space for hybrid learning. Along this, distance learning's definition and pedagogy have also changed due to the improvement of technology and other means related to education. Through the internet, Learning Management System (LMS), and other online learning platforms present today, distance

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learning have been taken into new ways, permitting distance learning to be conducted in real time. At the present time, different Learning Management System or LMS are being utilized, such as Google Classroom, Edmodo, and Moodle, to conduct online learning aside from softwares used as a web conferencing tool to manage live video sessions. According to Ostendorf (1997), instruction through live video session is the most well-known and fastest medium of instruction in the United States. This is also true in the Philippines wherein both blended-learning and flexible learning includes the use of online instruction.

With the abrupt incursion of the COVID-19 in the Philippines, all school institution had to suspend the conduction of face-to-face classes according to the directives of Department of Education (DepEd) and the Commission on Higher Education (CHED). However, DepEd, CHED, faculty and staff, students, and administrators are not really ready and still progressing in dealing with the new normal of learning amidst the pandemic (Villanueva, 2020). The Dep-Ed, specifically, have thought of a mix of radio and TV, modular, and online or electronic under the so-called "blended-learning." As for the CHED, they have come up with "flexible learning", which likewise incorporate e-learning or online learning that numerous schools and colleges in the Philippines have been doing even before. Although technology have provided a compromise in order to have continued access to education, there are still major problems encountered in distance learning such as the quality of instruction, efficiency of online learning schemes, attitudes of students, instructors, and administrators, and conduciveness of learning environment. Every single one of these affects the general nature of distance learning as an output. From multiple points of view, every one of these issues identifies with the others.

According to Afshin, Mohammadi, Raeisy, and Sarvestani (2019), the development and utilization of e-learning in the educational system have been quite possibly the main accomplishments of higher or tertiary education that can address problems of the educational system. One of the problems of the society is how to address the challenges/difficulties of online learning. The study's purpose was to explore students' experience of the challenges of online learning at Shiraz University of Medical Sciences (SUMS), a virtual school based at Shiraz, Iran.

As stated by Altug, Basay, Bolelli, Cetin, Esen, and Ozcan (2020), European nations were also surprised, just like other countries, not just in battling the COVID-19 pandemic or the spread of the virus, but also commencing distance learning as an alternative face-to-face schooling. Aside from the health and economic sectors, the pandemic have also an effect on the education system all around the world. Europe turned into the focal point of the sicknesses after the episode of pandemic in China. Shortly, it attained more alarming cases in the U.S. European nations are implementing distance learning and digital schooling to ensure the continuation of learning. Despite the fact that Sweden and Iceland have kept schools open, different areas had locked schools on March 16. The vast majority of the nations, whose public educational plans are very unique in relation to each other, had to swiftly adopt to distance learning even though they are uneasy and fully ready about it. The pandemic that have affected a vast number of students in Europe have had more impact to public schools.

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Chiwanza, Mapuranga, Musingafi, and Zebron (2015) conducted a study concerning the challenges and experiences of ODL from students of Zimbabwe Open University, a university in Zimbabwe, Africa. The research's objective was to discover the challenges tackled by students of at the ZOU. The methodology employed for the study was qualitative and quantitative approaches. The primary techniques used for collecting data were structured interviews and questionnaires, complemented by documentary/narrative review. Tables, rates, and frequencies were the central descriptive statistics utilized to evaluate and portray the results. The results indicated that ODL students had a hard time with a variety of hindrances in their course of learning. According to reports, the primary challenges were the insufficient time to study, limited access and difficulty in the usage of ICT, inefficient response and short supply of learning materials.

One of the recommendations was to make ZOU improve, and strive for the quality of education they delivered to attain efficient and balanced education and learning system, which meets the need of the students to the point that they would want to learn more and even recommend the university to others. On the online research article written by Shivangi Dhawan (2020), schools, universities, and colleges in India are still based only on conventional means of academic learning, which is face-to-face instruction in a room setting. Even though numerous school institutions have begun adopting to blended learning, some countries, such as India, are still left with the usual means of education. The unexpected outbreak of the deadly illness termed COVID-19 brought about by a Corona Virus (SARS-CoV-2) surprised the entire globe, which is why the World Health Organization (WHO) proclaimed it as a pandemic.

The present scenario challenged the system of education around the world and constrained instructors to adopt to an online method of educating for a limited span of time. Reluctant institutions had to change from traditional pedagogical approach into online teaching-learning. The cited work also included the analysis of Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, & Challenges or SWOC of online learning mediums throughout the time of crisis, and the relevance of online learning. The article also presented the development of EdTech Start-ups throughout the times of calamities and crisis (pandemic), and recommendations on how school institutions will address challenges relating to e-learning, such as having a high level of preparedness in order to be faster in adapting to sudden changes within the society and in utilizing other modes of delivery/instruction. As mentioned by Alberto, Baron, Baticulon, Clarion, Mabulay, Reyes, Rizada, Sy, and Tiu (2020) in their research, medical academic institutions had to suddenly shift from face-to-face learning to online learning. The research aimed to determine online learning barriers in the perception of medical learners in the Philippines, a developing country. The method utilized for collecting data was an electronic survey sent to the subjects of the study, which are solely Filipino medical students. The research instrument was comprised of Likert scale, multiple choice, and open-ended questions. Through applying descriptive statistics, the research learned that among the subjects, there are 93% that owed a smartphone and 83% had a desktop computer or laptop. A total of 79% used a postpaid internet payment whereas 19%

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of the subjects consumed prepaid mobile data to access resources in the online web. According to the research, there are currently only 45% (1,505 students) who regarded themselves as mentally and physically ready to engage in on-line learning. The barriers identified by the research were classified into five (5) classifications, namely, individual, technological, institutional, domestic, and community barriers. The primary challenges tackled by the subjects of the research were adjustment in styles of learning, conduciveness of home in doing duties and responsibilities, and little interaction between instructors and students.

METHODOLOGY

The study used quantitative and qualitative approach in gathering the data needed to surface the challenges experienced by the different students during the full swing hybrid learning. Further, it went through the simple diagnosis of the pervasive challenges encountered by students in the transition from on-line teaching to face-to face modality vis-à-vis hybrid learning as avenue to heightened more efficacious pedagogy responsive to the emerging needs of learners. The research was conducted in Saint Mary's University, a premier school in Region 2 which tapped hybrid learning and currently in the full swing implementation of face-to- face scheme. The instrument previously used in on-line evaluation and assessment of on-line facilitation of learning was adapted and modified to re-appropriate on the focus of the conducted study. The research instrument is appended with the link on google drive was used through the link provided to the selected 442 respondents from the different schools which included those enrolled for the current academic year of 2022-2-23 from first year to third year. Survey questionnaire crafted by the research team coming from multi-disciplinary areas was checked and validated by the ULRC and UREB prior to the conduct of the study. Data was collected from students through employing the use of survey questionnaire on google drive wherein both quantitative and qualitative questions were included to surface the emerging challenges experienced along transitioning to hybrid learning modality. An on-line survey form was utilized to collect data from 1st, 2nd, and 3rd year students from SMU. The gathered data was analyzed through descriptive statistics i.e., mean, median, mode, standard deviation, frequency, percentage, and cumulative percentage. Link on google form was sent to the various respondents. The research determined, assessed, and summarized the experiences and challenges of full swing face-to face learning along hybrid learning modality of students. The data was directly taken from the students' responses and analyzed to unravel the extent of readiness and challenges of the students on full swing face-to face modality along hybrid scheme. Challenges on adjustment surfaced became the bases of the program crafted meant to scaffold and manage hybrid learning.

RESULTS

The research conducted became an entry point to diagnose and determine the readiness of the learners on the full swing face-to-face learning modality with hybrid

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learning. It is assumed that transitioning to this pathway definitely posed several challenges among the various respondents from the different schools. Hence, the inclusion of intervention directed to the facilitation of learner centered teaching which includes hybrid learning. Such opened up innovations and interventions that would definitely bolster learner-centered teaching among students and teachers who previously went through on-line learning. While there are challenges on hand, pedagogies and digital applications are there to be maximized and be aligned with the expected learning outcomes in the teaching learning process.

Section 1: Profile of the Learners

Section 1 presents several tables that reflect the number of respondents, year, program, sex and modality of learning wanted during the initial year of the implementation of face-to-face learning for the school year 2022-2023. The profile of the learners who have transitioned from on-line learning to full swing face -to face hybrid learning is further categorizes to succinctly determine the extent of readiness of the learners.

Table 1: Profile of Learners: Year Level

Year Level	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	221	50.0	50.0	50.0
2	97	21.9	21.9	71.9
3	124	28.1	28.1	100.0
Total	442	100.0	100.0	

Table 1 shows the profile of learners along year level. Significantly, most of the respondents were freshmen with a total of 221 which includes 50 percent of the 442 students who participated in the survey checklist. This is followed by the junior students with a total of 124 which 28.1 percent of the over-all number of students. The sophomore got the smallest percentage of 21.9 which means there were only 97 respondents.

Table 2: Profile of Learners: Program and School

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid BSAR	22	5.0	5.0	5.0
BSCE	115	26.0	26.0	31.0
BSCpE	9	2.0	2.0	33.0
BSECE	5	1.1	1.1	34.2
BSEE	17	3.8	3.8	38.0
BSIT	7	1.6	1.6	39.6
SAB	73	16.5	16.5	56.1
SHANS	86	19.5	19.5	75.6
STEH	108	24.4	24.4	100.0
Total	442	100.0	100.0	

Table 2 presents the profile of learners along program and school enrolled. There were freshmen students who responded. Most of the students came from SEAIT, in particular they are freshmen and who are enrolled with Bachelor of Civil Engineering program. A total of 108 engineering students dominated the number of respondents.

Significantly, the school of SHANS with students who are enrolled in Bachelor of Science in Nursing included the least number of respondents. This could be justified as most of them are immersed in the different hospital and community work. As opined, there are programs which are categorized with more intricate schedule which is why even answering the survey question was seen difficult.

Table 3: Profile of Learners: Sex

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Female	267	60.4	60.4	60.4
Male	175	39.6	39.6	100.0
Total	442	100.0	100.0	

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There were 442 students coming from the various schools and different programs. Dominantly, the study was dominated by female, with 267 respondents in contrast with 175 males.

Table 4: Preferred Modality of Learning

Modality of Learning	Extent
Face-to-face	4.24 very great extent
Hybrid Learning	3.85 great extent

In terms of preferred modality of learning, most of the respondents chose face-to-face, with the **mean score of 4.24, very great extent**. Nonetheless, hybrid learning was also rated with a **mean score of 3.85, great extent**. Interestingly, several respondents signified the use of hybrid learning where both face-to-face and are on-line are maximized. It can be gleaned from the results that many of the learners selected the inclusion of both face-to-face and on-line modalities. The use of the LMS has been rated with a **mean score of 3.47** which means that it is significantly useful and can never be discounted as a platform in more effective learning modality. This confirms that hybrid learning has become more effective most specifically that most of the students just transitioned from a two year on-line modality of learning. Hybrid is defined as learning activities that involve a systematic combination of face-to-face and technology-based interactions between students and teachers, and it is an increasingly widespread approach in the education and training settings (Bliuc et al., 2007 as cited in Okuroglu & Alapar, 2022). More than ever, there are advantages that surfaced as many students found adjustments along the abrupt face-to-face learning modality. This means that while they were immersed with such modality, they still found on-line to be helpful in terms of complementing face-to-face learning.

The statement “ I find hybrid learning a practical and logical scheme during this post-pandemic era was rated **3.64 great extent**. This further reveals that many students prefer a hybrid modality of learning which is not limited to on-line scheme but blended in nature. While this modality surfaced the experiences of the learners who are on full-swing face-to-face, still there is a clamor that interspersed activities provided on line should be re-strengthened depending on the need and urgency.

Section 2: Level of Readiness on Full Swing Face-to-face through Hybrid Learning

Table 5: Level of Readiness on Full Swing Face-to-face through Hybrid Learning

QUESTIONS	MEAN
1. I find face- to-face learning enjoyable as I personally keep contact with my teachers and classmates.	4.24
2. I can easily reach out and contact my teachers during hybrid facilitation of learner-centered classes.	3.85

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3. I find the Learning Management System (LMS) operational and effective during this face-to face modality.	3.47
4. I can easily connect with the internet any time of the day.	3.10
5. I experience more challenges in on line class than in face to face.	3.64
6. I benefit much on on-line learning scheme in terms of information, formation and transformation	3.09
7. I experience the support and assistance of the school administration on various needs during this face -to face.	3.83
8. I take the subjects seriously in face- to- face classes since I am more ready than in on-line	4.13
9. I can manage my time with other activities while learning.	3.68
10. I enjoy on-line classes more than face to face.	2.67
11. I experience the help and consideration of my teachers on academic requirements during this full swing face-to-face learning with hybrid pedagogy.	3.80
12. I find our classroom more conducive for my hybrid learning.	3.73
13. I use my computer, smartphone and other devices in online learning without difficulty.	3.38
14. I submit my requirements on time during face-to face than on on-line classes.	4.00
15. I respond well with the method of examinations given in in face- to -face and LMS	3.96
16. I can do multi-tasking while in full swing -hybrid class.	3.40
17. I participate on synchronous meeting using Google Meet, Zoom, Webcon which are effective applications for classroom discussion and recitation even this full swing face-to-face hybrid learning.	3.40
18. I find hybrid learning a practical and logical scheme during this post-pandemic era.	3.64
19. I find hybrid learning a practical and logical scheme during this post-pandemic era.	3.65
20. I look forward to our face-to-face hybrid learning with enthusiasm and vigor every day	3.82
21. I experience clarity and accuracy of my learnings on- line.	3.02
22. I like on- line learning better than face- to- face.	2.57
23. I show readiness with full swing face-to-face with hybrid learning.	3.67
24. I find on-line learning more affordable than in face to face.	3.65
25. I feel lighter in terms of academic pressures in full swing face- to- face along with hybrid learning	3.49
OVERALL MEAN	3.56

Table 5 reveals that level of readiness of the various respondents on full- swing face -to-face was rated **3.56 qualified as great extent**. This means that the students' response on hybrid full swing face- to- face is significantly attuned with their expectations on the initial implementation of such modality after the two- year on-line scheme of learning. Further, the statement **"I like on-line learning better than face- to- face "** was rated the lowest mean score of 2.57, **moderate extent**. This confirms that face -to-face hybrid learning

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is much appreciated over pure on- line learning modality. In similar fashion, the statement “ ***I take the subjects seriously in face- to- face classes since I am more ready than in on- line***” was rated the second highest with the mean score of **4.13, very great extent** which is amplifies the preference of hybrid face-to face learning over single on-line modality. Interestingly, the statement “***I submit my requirements on time during face-to face than on on-line classes***” was rated with a mean score of **4.00 qualified as great extent**. As emphasized by Yang, F., & Yutai, R. (2022) blended learning is a combination of traditional face-to-face teaching and digital learning, but this combination is not a mechanical superimposition of learning styles, but a rational product of the process of informatization in education, a new way of learning that emerges from reflecting on the application of learning theories and technologies when attempts to reform or replace traditional classroom teaching with E-learning are not as effective as they could be. This then presupposes the use of both face-to-face and on-line learning. Further, the conducted study significantly affirmed the wanting and preference of face-to-face along with computer aided mode of the delivery of lesson. The statement” I look forward to our face-to-face hybrid learning with enthusiasm and vigor every day” has been rated **3.82, great extent** which clearly affirms the edge of hybrid face-to-face learning over on-line learning. The statements “***I feel lighter in terms of academic pressures in full swing face- to- face along with hybrid learning***” rated **3.49 qualified as great extent**” and “***I show readiness with full swing face-to-face with hybrid learning***” were rated to **a great** extent with mean scores of **3.49 and 3.67** respectively.

Significantly, the statement “ ***I find hybrid learning a practical and logical scheme during this post- pandemic era***” was rated with a mean score of **3.64** which is to a **great extent**. This implies the functionality of hybrid learning among the 442 respondents. As affirmed by Liu et al. (2016 as cited in Okuroglu & Alapar, 2022) hybrid learning appears to be more effective than non-hybrid instruction for knowledge acquisition in health professions. This applies so much among others in so far as many of the respondents also came from the School of Health and Sciences who practically needed the scheme to heighten multi-faceted learning.

Section 3: Challenges and Experiences encountered by the respondents on full swing face-to-face modality blended with hybrid learning

Table 6: Challenges and experiences Encountered

Challenges and experiences	Number of students
Adjustments	157
Time	67
No reason mentioned	66
Financial	42
Internet connection	31
Transportation	30
Requirements	22

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Attitude	16
Teachers	11
TOTAL OF RESPONDENTS	442

Table 6 reveals the various challenges encountered by the respondents. Significantly, there were 157 respondents who targeted adjustments as the main reason for the challenges made. This was followed by 67 students who mentioned time as one of the difficult things they experienced in having the full-swing hybrid face-to-face learning modality. Sixty-six students however did not put any reason. There were also 42 students who revealed that financial concerns were seen tough more so that there were many who did not have stable income after the pandemic. Thirty-one students also mentioned the unstable internet connection which means that even after the pandemic, this is still seen as the impending danger for hybrid learning among others. In terms of transportation, there were 30 students who found difficulty commuting after the 2 year on-line modality of learning, There were also 22 students who highlighted the challenge on submission of requirements they need to produce. Further, sixteen students revealed that their attitude also became a challenge as there was difficulty making adjustments. This can be affirmed with the students revelation that they have developed complacency during the pandemic time and somehow wanted to stay at home. There were also 11 students who explicitly mentioned some challenges rooting from their teachers. Over-all from the 442 respondents, it is evident that challenges were experienced in diverse ways and gravity.

Section 4: Intervention to be provided by teachers and students to bolster the facilitation of learner-centered teaching in the post- pandemic era

The study arrived at an intervention to bolters the facilitation of learner-centered teaching in the post pandemic era that is aligned with the existing needs of the respondents as well as the other students who sought some challenges on hybrid learning. Significantly, the scaffolding and managing of the hybrid learning can be achieved to bolster the learning efficaciously. Indeed, it can be surmised that even face-to-face has been initiated for academic year 2022-2023, once can never discount the huge contribution of hybrid learning modality.

Section 5: The measure of the effectivity of the intervention among stakeholders

The study revealed the multi-faceted plight of the different stakeholders on the hybrid full-swing-face-to-face learning scheme. Diverse challenges were experienced. Significantly, while there were 157 out from 442 respondents who mentioned adjustments as the prime reason the struggles they encountered, the extent of their readiness with the mean score of **3.56** *qualified as great extent* fueled their interest to complete and accomplished their tasks for the hybrid learning modality.

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CONCLUSION

The study revealed the multi-faceted plight of the different stakeholders on the hybrid full-swing-face-to-face learning scheme. Diverse challenges were experienced. Significantly, most of the respondents were female freshmen which included fifty percent of four-hundred forty-two contrasted to the 124 junior and 97 sophomore students. Readiness among the students was evident. This reveals that the students' response on hybrid full swing face- to- face is positively attuned with their expectations on the initial implementation of such modality after the two- year on-line scheme of learning. Challenges specifically on adjustments were noted as the crucial reasons that confronted the students. The study arrived at an intervention to bolters the facilitation of learner-centered teaching in the post pandemic era that is aligned with the existing needs of the respondents as well as the other students who sought some challenges on hybrid learning. The scaffolding and managing of the hybrid learning can be achieved to bolster the learning efficaciously. Hybrid learning environment introduces opportunities for educational leaders, teachers and learners in finding alternative approaches to enhance traditional brick and mortar setting. Indeed, there is no single pedagogy and strategy to respond to the emerging needs of diverse learners.

RECOMMENDATIONS

There are challenges which are unprecedented in determining the extent of readiness of the learners transitioning to full swing face-to-face with hybrid learning. Along this, face -to-face learning modality may be more effective among diverse learners but should be at the same time carried out with the applications of hybrid learning. Diagnosis and assessment of the extent of readiness of students should be seriously taken. Inspired pedagogies and methods are made available to aid and assist students in their needs. Interventions should be planned to respond to the psychology of providing learner-centered instruction. Continuing training, seminar, webinar and use of hybrid learning in this transition period should be provided in this post-pandemic era. Maximization of the use of hybrid learning is paramount in the articulation and the implementation of standards along effective pedagogy and learning. Joint productive activity language development, contextualization, challenging activities and instructional conversation are opportunities for bolstering hybrid learning.

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